

Applying Open Science principles to make a better use of IOTC data

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Open Science pillars (UNESCO)

+ Context of reproducibility crisis

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Open Science: how ?

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Context of [reproducibility crisis](#) => work can be replicated with:

- **data** :
 - data repositories to assign DOIs
 - implement **standards** : data structure and formats
 - **data papers**
- **code**
 - forge / **git**
 - assign **identifiers** : e.g. DOI, [Software Heritage](#)
- **environment** :
 - versions of programming language and related packages (R, Python):
e.g. renv
 - also the OS and system packages
- Standards to foster **interoperability**

Current IOTC Website will disappear !

You see a problem, I see an opportunity !

The screenshot shows the IOTC website interface. At the top, there is a blue header with the FAO logo and text: "Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations". To the right, there are links for "Contact us" and "Login", and a search bar with a "Search" button and flags for the United Kingdom and France. Below the header, the main navigation bar includes "Home", "The Commission", "Science", "Compliance", "Data", "Projects", "Meetings", "Documents", "News", and "Educational Tools". The main content area features a "QUICK LINKS" sidebar on the left with items like "Home", "Allocation estimations", "Capacity building", "Conservation and management measures", "E-PSM application", "IOTC Circulars", "IOTC Science Glossary", "IUU Vessel list", "Interactive data browser", "Performance Review", "Statdoc Validation", "Stock Status Dashboard", "Vessel records", "e-MARIS", and "e-RAV". The central part of the page has a large image of a school of tuna swimming underwater. Below the image, there is a paragraph of text: "The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC) is an intergovernmental organisation responsible for the management of tuna and tuna-like species in the Indian Ocean. It works to achieve this by promoting cooperation among its Contracting Parties (Members) and Cooperating Non-Contracting Parties in order to ensure the conservation and appropriate utilisation of fish stocks and encouraging the sustainable development of fisheries. [more...]" At the bottom, there is a "LATEST NEWS" section with two news items: "VESSELS CHARTERING IN THE IOTC AREA OF COMPETENCE. TANZANIA - OMAN" dated 26 November 2025 and "A COMMUNICATION FROM VANUATU" dated 11 November 2025. There is also a link for "all news".

Open Science: good practices for IOTC ?

IOTC scientific work will become more reproducible by sharing :

- **data** along with **metadata** (data dictionaries, [code lists](#)..)
- **code** : e.g. [BET stock assessment](#)
- **execution environment** : easy to access, restore, deploy..
- other scientific resources :
 - [forms](#),
 - [reports](#),
 - **working papers**,
 - **slides**,
 - ...and other educational resources

Long term access ensured and easy by assigning DOIs with e.g. [Zenodo](#)

Open Science: benefits ?

Reproducible work:

- saves **time**
- **trust** : reviewers of an article can check / replicate
- can be **reused** in other domains
- increase **citations**
- can be **deployed** on a server: e.g.
 - Shiny app
 - Stock assessment model and reproduce specific runs
 - HPC (High Performance computing)
 - ...

Cost ?

- **psychological** (may be counterintuitive)
- lower efficiency ? Slowing down at first..

Open Science: interoperability ?

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Standards to foster **interoperability** for fisheries data

- data structures :
 - fisheries: [CWP](#)
 - biodiversity: [GBIF](#)
- data formats :
 - csv or parquet rather than xlsx
 - spatial : e.g. GeoPackage rather than Shapefile.
- Open-source software (OSS) : QGIS, [GeoServer](#)
- runtime environment : Docker ..

GeoServer

Open Science: life cycle of digital objects

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Different version DOIs to manage the life stages of a dataset changing over time

Example: Global Tuna Atlas

Mean annual distribution (2005 to 2015) of catches of major tuna species

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Example: Global Tuna Atlas

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Example: IOTC Code Lists

The screenshot shows a Zenodo dataset page. At the top, the Zenodo logo is on the left, a search bar in the center, and 'Communities' and 'My dashboard' on the right. Below the search bar, there are 'Log in' and 'Sign up' buttons. The dataset is titled 'Reference Data – IOTC Code Lists for Fisheries Statistics' and is published by the 'Indian Ocean Tuna Commission'. It was published on June 26, 2025, and is version v1. The page shows 139 views and 43 downloads. The dataset is available in CSV, RDA, and Parquet formats. The data curator is the IOTC Secretariat and the data manager is Emmanuel Chassot. The page also includes a description of the dataset, a list of external resources (OpenAIRE), and a cookie consent banner at the bottom.

zenodo Search records... Communities My dashboard Log in Sign up

Indian Ocean Tuna Commission

Published June 26, 2025 | Version v1 Dataset Open

Reference Data – IOTC Code Lists for Fisheries Statistics

Indian Ocean Tuna Commission¹

Contributors

Data curator: IOTC Secretariat¹

Data manager: CHASSOT, Emmanuel¹

Show affiliations

Show affiliations

This dataset contains the complete set of reference data (code lists) maintained by the IOTC Secretariat to support the standardisation, validation, and integration of fisheries statistical data. These code lists are used across all data collection and reporting frameworks under the IOTC mandate and include controlled vocabularies for vessel types, gear types, species, areas, flag States, and other attributes relevant to tuna and tuna-like species fisheries. The code lists are made available in three tabular formats — **CSV**, **RDA** (R binary), and **Parquet** — to facilitate accessibility and interoperability across data science environments. They are also distributed as an **R library** via the [IOTC Secretariat GitHub repository](#), and mirrored by the [Fisheries Data Interoperability Working Group \(FDIWG\)](#) for broader interoperability within the fisheries data community. The dataset is versioned to ensure reproducibility and traceability in the context of the IOTC scientific process and wider scientific analyses.

The code lists are maintained and published by the IOTC Secretariat, which serves as the hosting institution responsible for their curation and periodic updates.

Files

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Example: Size Class data

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Example: Stock assessment

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GitHub

 D4SCIENCE

Example: Infrastructures

Deployment on any infrastructure (beyond your local PC) :

- physical : IOTC or FAO servers
- virtual : e.g. EOSC [Blue-Cloud 2026](#), [EDITO-Infra](#), google cloud..

All of this being possible at “no cost”...

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Current IOTC Website will disappear !

...but all resources with a DOI will remain online with the same URL for the next 20 years at least, they can feed the new site but not only.

A screenshot of a Zenodo dataset page. The page title is 'Reference Data – IOTC Code Lists for Fisheries Statistics'. It shows the dataset was published on June 26, 2025, and is version v1. The page has 139 views and 43 downloads. The dataset is maintained by the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC) Secretariat. The data curator is IOTC Secretariat and the data manager is CHASSOT, Emmanuel. The page includes a detailed description of the dataset, which contains reference data (code lists) for fisheries statistics, used for standardisation and integration. It also mentions that the data is available in CSV, RDA, and Parquet formats and is mirrored in a GitHub repository. A footer cookie notice is visible at the bottom of the page.

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Files

139 VIEWS 43 DOWNLOADS Show more details

Versions

Version	Published
Version v1	Jun 26, 2025

10.5281/zenodo.15743875

Cite all versions? You can cite all versions by using the DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15743874. This DOI represents all versions, and will always resolve to the latest one. Read more.

External resources

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 OpenAIRE

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Conclusion - Outlooks

Open Science good practices are recommended worldwide:

- reproducibility crisis
- in summary :
 - what should be shared: working papers, data, code, runtime environment..
 - how ? data repositories (e.g. Zenodo / GBIF..), infrastructures (GitHub, ..)
- for who ?
 - IOTC
 - CPCs
 - Consultants / Sub-contractors : very easy when you pay

We recommend that IOTC adopt these good practices by default and ASAP, making the Website migration an opportunity.

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This work has received support from the current HORIZON BlueCloud 2026 (grant No. [101094227](#)) and past European OpenAIRE-Connect H2020 research project (grant No. [731011](#)).

 eOSC Node

Digital Twin of the Ocean

Environment

Other examples ?

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- OFCF Photo library => IOTC community ? Without transferring ownership
- IODA : Indian Ocean Digital Atlas to be deployed in Sri Lanka
- GTA vs FishStatJ comparison to be reconducted every year ?
- GBIF / Darwin Core, DOI assigned by data repositories GBIF, Zenodo:
 - size class data
 - IOTTP data
 - biological database
- ...